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The Potential Role of Information and Communication Technologies in improving Education quality in Sub-Saharan Africa

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ABSTRACT

Sub-Saharan Africa (SSA) is one of the least developed regions in the world. In an attempt to catch up in the long term, those countries need to rely upon several factors simultaneously. Factors among which economy, governance and education occupy the first places. Concerning education, the situation remains worrying and most SSA countries are still far from achieving quality education, which is a prerequisite for the developmental goals targeted by most of these countries by 2050. In this documentary research, authors analyze the major problems faced by the education sector in SSA. The analysis has revealed that the education sector in SSA is disrupted by critical issues including the inactive education system, the limited access to education, the inadequate educational infrastructure, the problem of teachers training, the mismatch between training and employment, the low household income, the political instability and insecurity. They therefore posit the harmonious integration of ICT as having a crucial role to play for the effective improvement of quality education worldwide. ICT integration has become an asset to improving education and achieving sustainable development. Several countries have implemented ICT and gradually integrated new technologies in curricula, pedagogy, equipment and training. Authors conclude the analysis by recommending political and educational leaders in SSA countries invest more energy and resources in the effective integration of ICT into education systems. This requires a critical analysis of education problems and problems of integrating technologies into education. Analysis which must absolutely lead to the implementation of strategies for resolving these problems in the medium and long term.

Keywords

Sub-Saharan Africa, Quality Education, Information and Communication Technologies, Challenges

Introduction

Several studies have established that the human development indices of sub-Saharan Africa (SSA) countries are among the lowest on the globe [1][2]. Indeed, extreme poverty is still a major challenge for many countries in SSA despite the performance recorded in the framework of the Millennium Development Goals (MDGs). The Development policies that aimed at improving the living conditions of populations have not yet succeeded in eradicating this phenomenon in SSA [3]. To succeed in reversing this trend and eradicate poverty, SSA

countries need to and act on several factors put together. One of the determining factors that must be improved in SSA countries is the quality of education. Indeed, several studies have highlighted the determining role of education for poverty eradication and sustainable development [4][3]. Education has been human development's driving force overtime and the main driver of development in all its dimensions [5][6][7]. Europe 2020 strategy has highlighted the key role of education in achieving sustainable development [8]. In terms of Education, the Europe 2020 strategy has set two targets which consist in reducing the number of early school leavers and increasing the number of young adults who have completed tertiary education [9]. The focus on education in Europe 2020 strategy shows the centrality of education in sustainable development. Similarly, their 2030 Agenda has also highlighted the central role of education. In fact, education is one of the 17 goals set for sustainable development. Primarily, the Sustainable Development Goal 4 (SDG 4) of the 2030 Agenda aims to ensure quality education and promote lifelong learning opportunities for everyone by 2030 [10]. To significantly reduce poverty, it is important to act on education, because of its impact on several levels on development. For example, [Mazza 2021](#) [9] highlighted the fact that education has a positive effect on employability, and therefore on poverty reduction. On the other hand, education is a process that simultaneously allows the individual, society and the State to acquire human capital that promotes economic growth and the distribution of income. However significantly improving the quality of education in SSA is a difficult task, given the numerous scourges that plague education sector in most countries in this region of the world. Education issues in SSA are numerous, and in the first section, we only focus on the most relevant and recurrent ones. In the second section, we present ICT as a determining factor for the significant improvement of quality education in SSA. We conclude by giving advices to countries leaders for a smooth integration of ICT in education in order to accomplish quality education.

Education's Challenges in Sub-Saharan African Countries

Nowadays, excellence in education appears to be the only weapon to deal with the ever-increasing unforeseen events of the globe. As a result, leaders of countries worldwide are constantly thinking on the new strategies to improve educational outcomes in order to be ahead of the future. However, SSA remains a region of the world which is very exposed to the uncertainties of the future in the sense that education systems remain primary and unsuited to contemporary needs and challenges. Several fundamental parameters cause issues for education systems in African countries, and which, at the same time, reveal the low level of performance of these education systems. These include the inactive education system, the limited access to education, the inadequate educational infrastructure, the problem of teachers training, the mismatch between training and employment, the low household income, the political instability and insecurity.

An inactive education system

Several authors have denounced the inertia of education systems in SSA countries [11]. Indeed, in many SSA countries, the higher education system and the majority of its contents date back to the colonial times and are not adapted to the current development challenges of concerned countries. Since the end of the colonial period,

African schools have kept the colonial philosophy and mission which does not fit with the characteristics of a school for development. SSA countries have so far failed to set up their own education systems adapted to their needs and realities.

Limited access to education

Another major problem of education in SSA is the exclusion of a large number of young people from quality education. Indeed, despite the fact that access to education is improving globally, UNESCO (2012) [12] estimated at more than 617 million the number of children who still do not manage to benefit from a minimum level of competence in reading and mathematics. A significant proportion of this figure is in SSA, where more than 30 million children are deprived of basic education. Those most exposed to the scourge of young people's limited access to quality education are women and people living in rural areas. This phenomenon results in the fact that adult literacy rates in SSA are among the lowest on the planet. Another consequence of this phenomenon is the fact that the number of out-of-school children in this region of the world is the highest in the world [13].

Inadequate educational infrastructure

In most SSA countries, it is still difficult to talk about quality education. One of the factors that hinders access to quality education is the lack of infrastructure or its inadequacy to the needs of contemporary education. The obsolescence of school infrastructure, the disrepair of educational environments, and the insufficiency of buildings which results in overcrowding in classrooms are important factors that prevent the supply of quality education in SSA [15]. The harmful effects of the lack of educational infrastructure are accentuated by the vertiginous demographic growth which amplifies the educational crisis [16].

The problem of teachers training

Another recurring problem in SSA education is the often inadequate or absent training of teachers. Indeed, several private kindergartens, primary and secondary schools are unable to employ teachers from training schools recognized by the state institutions in charge of education. Under these conditions, these private schools are likely to hire young people who improvise themselves as teachers without having undergone any training and without having any notion of pedagogy. St-Armand & Talake (2019) [13] also denounced teacher training by deeming this training ineffective. These authors believe that the training offered to teachers is often unsuitable and sometimes does not correspond to the specific needs of students.

The mismatch between training and employment

Guiake & Tianxue (2019) [11] believe that despite the fundamental role of higher education in economic growth of any country, Cameroon state universities' curricula are not relevant to meet the challenges of new graduates and the needs of the country which aspires to emerge by 2035. The authors stated that “...*there is no significant link between the nature of the programs and courses taught in Cameroonian state universities and the knowledge and skills needed for the labour market, and reach its emergence*”. This situation, which is widespread in SSA countries, can be explained by the fact that the social and human sciences occupy a

prominent place in almost all state universities. However, it has been proven that the social sciences and humanities are less important in shaping valuable human capital for economic purposes [11][15]. Nowadays, most countries in the world direct their educational system towards socioeconomic-based disciplines. According to [OECD \(2018\)](#) [15], students entering to the higher education are more likely to be enrolled in STEM fields than any others, but this trend is not true in most SSA countries like Cameroon, where universities continue to produce graduates in unproductive programs. This phenomenon results in high unemployment rates among young graduates [16].

Low household income

In general, the standard of living is very low in most SSA countries, which has a profound impact on access to education quality for young people in this region of the world. Whether in primary, secondary or tertiary, there is generally a two-speed education in the sense that there are on the one hand the educational institutions of reference which offer a high-level education reserved for children from rich families, and on the other hand the traditional institutions which offer mass education because the costs of training are more affordable there. Given the demand for training, which is growing exponentially due to the demographic explosion, these traditional institutions are generally characterized by understaffing which has a negative influence on education quality. Indeed, under these conditions it is impossible for teachers to follow the progression of the level of each student. Despite the low quality of education in this type of school, most parents have no choice but to send their children there. Many authors have demonstrated that low incomes reduce household's ability to send their children to good schools [17][18]. If for lack of sufficient financial means, many parents are obliged to send their children to schools which offer a low level of education, there are also many children who are forced to stop their studies prematurely for lack of funding. The financial vulnerability of households therefore appears to be an obstacle to education quality in SSA.

Political instability and insecurity

Another factor that works against education in SSA countries is the climate of political instability and recurrent armed conflicts. For example, many parts of West and Central Africa are experiencing ever-increasing hostilities against education. These hostilities are committed by warring factions. According to [UNICEF \(2019\)](#) [19], 742 verified attacks on schools were committed across the globe in 2018. More than a quarter of these attacks occurred in five countries in West and Central Africa. Between the end of 2017 and the middle of 2019, the number of schools forced to close due to insecurity caused by armed conflicts in West and Central Africa had tripled. UNICEF [19] revealed that in June 2019, more than 1.91 million children and nearly 44,000 teachers were affected by the closure of 9,271 schools. This situation arises from the fact that in the countries of the central Sahel (Burkina Faso, Mali and Niger) and in the countries of the Lake Chad basin (Cameroon, Nigeria and Chad), a large part of these hostilities is fueled by ideological opposition to what is perceived as Western-style education. This implies that students, teachers, administrators and infrastructure are deliberately targeted, further disrupting access to quality education. Faced with the risk of armed attacks, local

communities are scared, and several schools are closing their doors, forcing teachers and students to stay at home.

Considering the various issues analyzed in the previous paragraphs, it is urgent that the governments of various SSA countries make more efforts to significantly improve the quality of education in their country. To do so, they must implement effective and sustainable strategies such as the solutions proposed by researchers who have worked on the problems of education in SSA. Among the many proposed solutions, ICT integration is one of the most likely to impact the quality of education in SSA.

The Potential role of ICT in improving the quality of Education in Sub-Saharan Africa

ICT stands for “Information and communication technology”. It refers to technologies that provide access to information through telecommunication. It is similar to Information Technology (IT) but focuses primarily on communication technologies. This includes the internet, wireless networks, cell phones and other communication media. It means more opportunities to ICT in teacher training programs nowadays and improve quality and effectiveness of teaching. According to [UNESCO \(2010\)](#) “ICT is a scientific, technological and engineering discipline and management technique used in handling information, its application and association with social, economic and cultural matters” [20].

As we mentioned in the previous section, developing countries like those in SSA are characterized by poor education system because efforts to improve education quality and the learning effectiveness crippled by many issues affecting education sector [21]. Faced with numerous problems of education, all governments, within their budgetary constraints, are looking for solutions to offer their youth the best education [22]. According to [UNESCO \(2010\)](#) [21], effective learning is the consequence of quality education which also depends on resources, approaches and strategies used by teachers and students. Pedagogical integration of ICT is one of the principal strategies used by teachers and students to improve teaching and learning quality. Indeed, ICT have evolved recently, which has provided various development opportunities in many sectors. Several countries have seized opportunities offered by ICT in many areas. The influence of ICT in education is pushing many governments to adopts those technologies for a greater efficiency and effectiveness of their education systems [23]. The benefits of ICT in education are evident in terms of flexibility, accessibility, communication, interaction and variety of teaching and learning modes. So, ICT appear to be tools for learning quality [24]. ICT is beneficial in most where knowledge and communication play a key role: those technologies improve teaching and learning processes and also improve academic achievement. Moreover, those technologies strengthen students’ motivation and also promotes communication between academic leaders, teachers and parents. ICT also enable the networking and coordination between schools, and provide better management within school [25].

In a century where knowledge is the most essential asset due to the rapid evolution of society and the global economy, education systems in SSA countries must equip young Africans with new skills and competences that will enable them to seize new opportunities and actively contribute to Africa economic development.

Those aptitudes and skills are often referred to as “21st century skills”. This name stems from the fact that these skills are more related to the requirements of emerging economic development models than to the requirements of the industrial development models that were new a century ago, that are now outdated [26]. Today, it is essential for Sub-Saharan African countries to build a workforce endowed with all the aptitudes and skills that are adapted to the knowledge economies. These skills are linked to knowledge management, which take into account the processes related to the selection, acquisition, analysis and sharing of information through social networks. The academic environment is the only place where most African young people can acquire such skills and abilities. This aspect makes the integration of ICT in African educational environments not only essential, but also unavoidable.

Advanced economies have migrated from the manufacturing sector to information and knowledge services. Knowledge then expands exponentially, while becoming more specialized. Today, ICTs are the main means of disseminating knowledge. These technologies transform overall the way of working, learning and living in general. Skills such as decentralized decision making, information sharing, teamwork and innovation are mandatory in today businesses.

Research conducted over the past decade has revealed how the increased use of new digital technologies has profoundly transformed social practices; these transformations are more pronounced for young people [27][28]. Such practices create a re-design of key skills and abilities, not defined at the system level, but in the everyday lives of people in our societies. An example is research on computer games and online communities [27][29], where problem solving is defined as a key element of such practices. Such problem-solving experiences among young people should inform us about how we design assessment tasks and define key competencies. As a result, new standards of what African students should be able to do have to replace the basic skills and knowledge expected from the past. To meet this challenge, African schools need to be transformed to enable students to acquire sophisticated thinking, flexible problem solving, and the collaborative and communicative skills they will need to succeed in their professional and personal lives. New conceptions of standards and the assessment of education in Africa are an essential strategy for carrying out the necessary transformation. These standards and assessments can both draw attention to the capabilities needed and provide data to leverage and assess system change. Technology may serve as both a driver and a lever for transformation in all areas and in all sectors of activity in Sub-Saharan African countries.

It has been universally established that investments in public education make a significant contribution to the vitality of communities and the strengthening of national prosperity. Socio-economic and environmental challenges make education issues even more critical nowadays. Indeed, it is formal and informal education that prepares today's children to assume their adult role in the future, as citizens, employees, managers, parents, entrepreneurs [30]. In order to fully play their role as adults of tomorrow, young African people must develop a series of skills, competencies and knowledge that will facilitate their mastery and application of languages, mathematics and other subjects. At the same time, African business leaders and governments may increasingly

call on schools to develop skills in learners such as problem-solving, critical thinking, communication, collaboration, and self-management. Without an effective integration of ICT in educational systems, learners cannot acquire those skills. Hence the role of ICT in SSA education is decisive.

The pedagogical scope of ICT in the learning process in schools is widely emphasized in the scientific literature in Africa. Most of this work highlights opportunities to use ICT to support learning, help students find documents on Internet and develop so-called cross-cutting skills. ICT thus promotes goal-based pedagogy and collaborative learning that many researchers and educators [31][32] recommend in the process of co-building knowledge. The teacher who integrates ICT into his pedagogical practice acts as a guide and facilitator for learners and offers them motivating and meaningful situations as well as resources that enable them to implement their skills during the learning activity. A report of UNESCO (2007) [33] presents ICT as potential drivers of growth and empowerment, making ICTs potentially positively impacting education. As the school is an institution that has the responsibility to train students in the skills they need for their social and economic integration [34], it cannot ignore Technologies or risk being discredited. The pedagogical integration of ICT now seems unavoidable in order to promote educational success for African students, enhance the professionalism of African teachers and encourage managerial leadership. In addition, ICT may be used to fosters collaboration between African schools and student's family.

Several researchers argue that ICT has a cross-cutting and widespread use for teaching [35] [36] [37] [38] [39]. ICT offers a variety of educational benefits. Indeed, ICTs offer greater flexibility, accessibility, communication, and foster interactions. The centrality and importance of ICT is evident today, the pedagogical integration of ICT now seems inevitable in order to promote the educational success of students, enhance the professionalism of teachers and encourage managerial leadership, and even promote collaboration between the school and the family. ICT provides attractive and rapidly evolving learning environments. These technologies are blurring the boundaries between formal and informal education and encourage teachers to develop new methods to pass on their teachings to students, thus facilitating their learning. These technologies offer extraordinary opportunities to improve the quality of the learning environment in SSA countries. These are all the conditions that allow learning to take shape, at work, at school or at home [40]. According to [41], ICT allows for the development of more effective and relevant educational strategies than traditional practices. ICT also helps to diversify teaching and learning. All these advantages of ICT must be well used to significantly improve the quality of education in SSA countries to face the contemporary challenges of Africa and the world.

In the new global agenda that now places ICT at the heart of learning processes [42], Africa is not an exception. Even in Africa's most landlocked villages or in Africa's modernized cities, no student seems indifferent to the growing and rapid expansion of ICT. Faced with this scale of ICT proliferation, many African leaders have become aware and are committed to ICT in education [43]. The following comments illustrate this situation.

President MUSEVENI of Uganda, at the launch of the NEPAD (New Partnership for Africa development) e-School project said: *“this technology will allow young people in this village to tap into the mainstream of information and knowledge, where they can learn and play, expand their imagination and creativity, and collaborate with their peers across the African continent and around the world.”* Abdelaziz BOUTEFLIKA, Algerian President in his address to the 14th African Union Summit on *“Information and Communication Technologies in Africa: Challenges and Prospects for Development”* in Addis Ababa on 31 January 2010 highlighted the importance of ICT in all vital areas of Africa's development. At the time, he insisted that ICT is now an indispensable tool. Alpha OUMAR KONARE, former president of Mali, believes that new technologies represent a major issue of emergence. He even argues that the ICT debate is obligatory for any country that aspires to modernity, because ICTs solve many problems relating to infrastructure, health, and education [44]. Kofi ANNAN at the World Summit on the Information Society in Tunis in November 2005 affirmed that the world is going through a time of rapid change where technologies play a key role in multiple areas of human activity. ICT affects the economic, social and cultural dimensions of the evolution of any society. Elizabeth OHENE, Ghana's Minister of State for Education and Sports, at the opening of the country's first NEPAD e-School recognized that the computer should no longer be seen as an improved typewriter, but as a tutor, organizer, presentation, a research officer, a data processor, an interactive catch-up and e-learning agent.

Despite the abundant discourse on the potential role of ICT in improving the quality of education in SSA, there is a great disparity in the implementation of strategies for the effective integration of ICT in education systems. Not all SSA countries are committed with the same enthusiasm for the effective integration of ICT in education. To highlight this disparity, a World Bank study authored by [Wallet \(2015\)](#) [45], a member of the UNESCO Institute for Statistics, reveals that among SSA countries, only 15 had an ICT integration policy in education in 2014, and only 12 out of 15 countries had a national plan for integrating ICT in education (see the following statistical table).

Table: SSA countries and policy on ICT in education, 2013-2014

Country has a policy on ICT in education		No policy or plan	No information
	Only for upper secondary education		
Angola, Botswana, Côte d'Ivoire, Eritrea, Gambia, Mauritius, Rwanda, Sao Tome and Principe, South Africa, Uganda and Zambia	Ethiopia, Djibouti and Togo	Cameroon, Comoros, Congo, Guinea, Lesotho and Madagascar	Benin, Burundi, Cabo Verde, Central Africa Republic, Chad, Democratic Republic of Congo, Equatorial Guinea, Gabon, Guinea-Bissau, Malawi, Mali, Namibia, Nigeria, Senegal, Sierra Leone, Somalia, Swaziland, United Republic of Tanzania and Zimbabwe
Country has a national plan on ICT in education			
Botswana, Burkina Faso, Côte d'Ivoire, Gambia, Kenya, Liberia, Mozambique, Niger, Sao Tome and Principe, South Africa, Uganda and Zambia			

Notes: Data for South Africa reflect 2011; data for Angola, Botswana, Togo and Zambia reflect 2012; and data for Ethiopia, Gambia, Kenya, Liberia, Mauritius and Mozambique reflect 2014.

Source: *UIS statistical database, 2015 (Statistical Table 1); World Bank, 2015.*

Given the numerous advantages that ICTs offer for improving the quality of education, SSA countries have a great interest in using these technologies to strengthen their education systems and boost their development. According to Al-Khasawneh [46], the process of technological diffusion is generally the economic lever that provides a competitive advantage to nations. He believes that developing countries such as those in SSA should invest more in technology education to produce the labor needed to have a high technological advantage. Unfortunately, SSA countries still appear to have failed to implement an effective ICT's integration policies in education system to significantly improve the quality of education. It is noticeable that educational reforms for ICTs' integration in Sub-Saharan education systems have not yet produced the desired results. Because of ICTs' issues in education, scholars such as Balanskat et al. [47] and Bingimlas [48] argue that it is necessary to analyze the challenges of using ICT in education in order to provide solutions to educators who can eventually successfully adopt technologies.

Conclusion

This research has highlighted the need to achieve education quality in SSA in order to impact the development of those countries. The analysis has revealed that many problems are disrupting the education sector in SSA including the inactive education system, the limited access to education, the inadequate educational infrastructure, the problem of teachers training, the mismatch between training and employment, the low household income, the political instability

and insecurity. Finally, the harmonious integration of ICT was posited as having a crucial role to play for the effective improvement of quality education in this sector, and therefore a major factor that can help to solve major problems related to education and development in SSA. However, it is unfortunate that ICT integration in education systems is facing numerous challenges in the region. The study has noted a great disparity in the implementation of ICT integration policies in education among the various countries of the sub-region. Political leaders and educational leaders are therefore recommended to undertake a critical analysis of the problems related to education and related to ICT integration in education systems, in order to implement relevant strategies to solve these various problems and significantly improve education quality.

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